

METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATION OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL READINESS INDICATORS OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED FREESTYLE WRESTLERS

Jurakhanov Khamidullo Khojimirzaivych

Senior teacher of the department Sports activities, NamSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933969>

Abstract: *In this article we used pedagogical testing methods to determine pre-competition readiness indicators and diagnose physical qualities of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers. We included them in the following group of tests: 1) the recovery process after loads and load tolerance were determined.*

Keywords: *freestyle wrestlers, technical-tactical, Olympic, In the position of a bridge, planning, research, throwing over the shoulder, throwing over the waist, throwing by wrapping the arm around the neck, throwing over the chest, long jump from standing position.*

ТЕКСТ НАУЧНОЙ РАБОТЫ НА ТЕМУ «МЕТОДИКА ОЦЕНКИ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ТЕХНИКО-ТАКТИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ БОРЦОВ ВОЛЬНОГО СТИЛЯ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ»

Аннотация: В данной статье мы использовали методы педагогического тестирования для определения показателей предсоревновательной подготовленности и диагностики физических качеств борцов вольного стиля высокой квалификации. Мы включили их в следующую группу тестов: 1) определяли процесс восстановления после нагрузок и переносимость нагрузок.

Ключевые слова: борцы вольного стиля, технико-тактические, олимпийские, в положении моста, планирование, исследование, бросок через плечо, бросок через пояс, бросок обхватом руки вокруг шеи, бросок через грудь, прыжок в длину с места позиция.

INTRODUCTION

Interest in the sport of freestyle wrestling is increasing worldwide, and special attention is being paid to its development among young people and adults. Growing talented athletes in Olympic sports regularly leads to increased competition, increased the intensity of the training process to the level of demand. This calls for research and formation of new methods for improving the training methods of qualified athletes. In particular, as a result of the competitions included in the program of the continental championships, world championships, and the Olympic Games, the sport of freestyle wrestling is finding its place in the world community. In order to ensure the participation of freestyle wrestlers in the above-mentioned competitions, large-scale works are being carried out in order to adapt the training system of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers to the requirements of the time. Today, one of the most important tasks facing all sports is the issue of proper and effective planning of athletes' pre-competition training. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PD-5368 of March 5, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports" [6], and Decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 122 of March 4, 2020 " "On measures to further improve the system of selection of athletes to national sports teams" [2], this dissertation research serves to a certain extent the implementation of the tasks defined in other regulatory legal documents related to this field. In the world, extensive scientific research is being carried out: on the contribution of other sports close to or similar to freestyle wrestling to human physical development, the full expression of sports ethics, the proof of their effectiveness and further development, and the scientific justification of the training system of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers. In particular, a system was created based on the

development of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers for all types of wrestling, functional and physical training, technical-tactical actions and physical qualities. During training, there are opportunities to combine the types of exercises, their load, the description of rest after training, the number of training sessions, loads of different magnitudes and directions, as well as to change the rate and direction of the return of the microcycle process. However, the methods of studying, teaching and popularizing freestyle wrestling at the world level, pre-competition training of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers in the sport, and assessing their physical capabilities are aimed at predicting sports achievements.

We used pedagogical testing methods to determine pre-competition readiness indicators and diagnose physical qualities of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers. We included them in the following group of tests: 1) the recovery process after loads and load tolerance were determined. To achieve the purpose of our research a pedagogical experiment was conducted in order to justify the effectiveness of our methodology focused on the evaluation and monitoring indicators of pre-competition training of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers in a sports school. A total of 28 wrestlers participated in the pedagogical research at the sports school specialized in individual wrestling sports of Namangan region. Participants in the pedagogical experiment (n=28) were divided into two groups: experimental group (EG) and control group (CG). The number of wrestlers in both groups was the same (n= 14). Exercises in the control group continued on the basis of traditional, program and charter , and in the experimental group, it was conducted based on the methodology developed and proposed by us . (See Table 1).

Table 1 Comparative statistical analysis of the indicators of technical and tactical training of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers before the study (n=28)

Control tests	Experience group n=14		Control group n=14		t	P
	($\bar{X} \pm s$)	V	($\bar{X} \pm s$)	V		
Throw over the shoulder 10 times (s).	15.7 ± 1.8 _ _	11 , 8	16 , 4 ± 1, 3	8 , 1	1 , 64	P>0.05
Throw over the waist 10 times. (s).	16.2 ± 1.4 _ _	9, 1	16 , 7 ± 1, 2	7 , 4	1.56	P>0.05
Throwing by wrapping arm around his neck 10 times. (s).	17, 4 ± 1.8	10 , 4	18, 1 ± 1.3	7, 4	1, 66	P>0.05
Throw over the breast 10 times. (s).	17 , 8 ± 1, 8	10, 2	18 , 5 ± 2, 1	1 1 , 5	1, 20	P>0.05
Carry out a combination of 4-point techniques to take a partner equal to your own weight from the hand to the upper parter in 30 seconds (number)	16 , 8 ± 2, 3	14, 3	15 , 8 ± 2, 1	1 3 , 1	1, 17	P>0.05
Performing a combination of 2 point methods by Carrying a partner equal to his own weight by the hand to the upper parter in 30 seconds (number)	17 , 4 ± 1, 4	8, 3	16 , 7 ± 1, 6	9, 2	1, 61	P>0.05
Perform a combination of 2 point techniques by Taking a partner equal to your own weight by the arm and transfer to a low parter in 30 seconds (number)	20 , 9 ± 2, 1	9, 9	20 , 4 ± 1, 4	7, 1	1, 11	P>0.05

Eg- Experimental group; Cg-Control group; n= number of participating athletes.

Throw over the waist. 10th time(s) 16.2 ± 1.4 cm in the experimental group, 16.7 ± 1.2 cm in the control group . A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.56$; $p<0.05$).

Throwing by wrapping arm around his neck 10 times, 17.4 ± 1.8 cm in the experimental group , 18.1 ± 1.3 cm in the control group . A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.66$; $p<0.05$).

Throw over the breast 10 time(s) in the experimental group 17.8 ± 1.8 cm , in the control group 18.5 ± 2.1 cm . A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.20$; $p<0.05$).

Performing a combination of 4-point methods by taking a partner of equal weight by the hand and transferring it to the upper part in 30 seconds (number) 16.8 ± 2.3 cm in the experimental group, 15.8 ± 2.1 cm in the control group . A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.17$; $p<0.05$).

Performing a combination of 2-point methods by pulling the partner's hand of equal weight and transferring it to the upper part in 30 seconds (number) 17.4 ± 2.3 cm in the experimental group, 16.7 ± 1.6 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.61$; $p<0.05$).

Performing a combination of 2-point methods by pulling the partner's hand of equal weight and transferring it to the lower part in 30 seconds (number) 20.9 ± 2.1 cm in the experimental group and 20.4 ± 2.4 cm in the control group . A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.11$; $p<0.05$).

According to the information obtained at the end of the research, the following was determined. In the table we can observe improvement in all fourteen indicators. For example, we found reliable statistical differences at the end of the experiment on the Stange test. (see table 2.)

In wrestling, rotations around the head in the bridge position 3 times to the right and left were 13.5 ± 0.7 cm in the experimental group, 13.2 ± 1.2 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=0.82$; $p<0.05$).

The 10 times rollover in the bridge position was 19.6 ± 2.1 cm in the experimental group, 20.2 ± 1.8 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.12$; $p<0.05$).

2 - picture. A diagram representing the statistical difference in the physical fitness indicators of the experimental and control groups of wrestlers at the beginning of the pedagogical experiment

The research was carried out on the basis of the traditional program and regulations intended for sports school institutions in the control group, and on the basis of the methodology developed and proposed by us in the experimental group.

According to the data obtained at the end of the study, the following was determined (see Table 2). In all fourteen indicators in the table

Table 2 Comparative statistical analysis of the indicators of technical and tactical readiness of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers at the end of the study (n=28)

Control tests	Experience group n=14		Control group n=14		t	P
	($\bar{x} \pm s$)	V	($\bar{x} \pm s$)	V		
Throw over the shoulder 10 times (s).	13,5 ± 1,1	8,1	14,7 ± 1,9	13,1	2,7	P < 0.05
Throw over the waist 10 times. (s).	14.1 ± 1.8	12,9	15,1 ± 1,1	7,5	2.3	P<0.05
Throwing by wrapping arm around his neck 10 times. (s).	14.5 ± 1.7	11,3	15,3 ± 1.2	7,1	2,2	P<0.05
Throw over the breast 10 times. (s).	15,1 ± 2,1	13,8	16,5 ± 1,7	10,7	2,8	P<0.01
Carry out a combination of 4-point techniques to take a partner equal to your own weight from the hand to the upper parter in 30 seconds (number)	18,3 ± 2,4	13,1	16,9 ± 2,4	14,1	2,23	P<0.05
Performing a combination of 2 point methods by Carrying a partner equal to his own weight by the hand to the upper parter in 30 seconds (number)	20,5 ± 2,3	11,2	18,8 ± 2,6	13,8	2,32	P<0.05
Perform a combination of 2 point techniques by Taking a partner equal to your own weight by the arm and transfer to a low parter in 30 seconds (number)	22,1 ± 2,5	11.3	20,4 ± 2,2	10,9	2,86	P<0.01

Throw over the shoulder 10 times (s) 13.5 ± 1.1 cm in the experimental group, 14.7 ± 1.9 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development (t=2.7; p<0.05).

Throw over the waist 10th time(s) 14.1 ± 1.8 cm in the experimental group , 15.1 ± 1.1 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development (t=2.3; p<0.05).

Throwing by wrapping arm around his neck 10 times, 14.5 ± 1.7 cm in the experimental group , 15.3 ± 1.2 cm in the control group . A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development (t=2.2; p<0.05).

Throw over the breast 10 time(s) in experimental group 15.1 ± 2.1 cm, in control group 16.5 ± 1.7 cm. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development (t=2.8; p<0.01).

Performing a combination of 4-point methods by taking a partner of equal weight by the hand and transferring it to the upper parter in 30 seconds (number) 18.3 ± 2.4 cm in the experimental group , 16.9 ± 2.4 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development (t=2.23; p<0.05).

Performing a combination of 2-point methods by pulling the partner's hand of equal weight and transferring it to the upper part in 30 seconds (number) 20.5 ± 2.3 cm in the experimental group, 18.8 ± 2.6 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=2.32$; $p<0.05$).

Performing a combination of 2-point methods by pulling the partner's hand of equal weight and transferring it to the lower part in 30 seconds (number) 22.1 ± 2.5 cm in the experimental group, 20.4 ± 2.2 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=2.86$; $p<0.01$).

CONCLUSION

Based on the above findings, the following general conclusions were reached. In particular, a system based on the development of functional and technical-tactical movements and physical qualities of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers for all types of wrestling was created. A pedagogical experiment was conducted in order to substantiate the effectiveness of our methodology aimed at evaluation and monitoring indicators of pre-competition training of highly qualified freestyle wrestlers. A total of 28 wrestlers participated in the pedagogical research at the sports school specialized in individual wrestling sports of Namangan region. Participants in the pedagogical experiment ($n=28$) were divided into two groups: experimental group (EG) and control group (CG). The number of wrestlers in both groups was the same ($n=14$). Exercises in the control group continued on the basis of traditional, program and charter, and in the experimental group it was conducted based on the methodology developed and proposed by us. Performing a combination of 2-point methods by pulling the partner's hand of equal weight and transferring it to the lower part in 30 seconds (number) 20.9 ± 2.1 cm in the experimental group and 20.4 ± 2.4 cm in the control group. A significant statistical difference was found in mathematical development ($t=1.11$; $p<0.05$).

According to the information obtained at the end of the research, the following was determined. In the table we can observe improvement in all fourteen indicators. For example, we found reliable statistical differences at the end of the experiment on the Stange test.

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